

RESULTS

ENGAGEMENT

UNIQUE AUTHORS

UNIQUE SITES

PERFORMANCE OVER TIME

1.8M Results

Results

— AVANGARD

Engagement

- - - AVANGARD

SHARE OF MEDIA TYPES

REACH VS ENGAGEMENT

What are the top themes?

TOP THEMES

TOP HASHTAGS

What is the sentiment of the conversation?

SHARE OF SENTIMENT

3579% Positive 3015% Neutral 13146% Negative

SENTIMENT OVER TIME

SENTIMENT KEY DRIVERS

TOP POSITIVE RESULTS

Author	Post	

TOP NEGATIVE RESULTS

Author	Post	
various Newspaper indiatimes.com 10/06/22 15:57 India	Times Top10: Tod... <i>More here What: As the Niti Aayog steps up to finalise the 'Battery Swapping Policy' for electric vehicles (EVs), automobile industry and some gove...</i>	

What are the demographics of your audience?

GENDER

NON-BINARY GENDER

138.5K Results

AGE

364.2K Results

TOP LANGUAGES

1.8M Results

TOP OCCUPATIONS

190.6K Results

TOP INTERESTS

489.3K Results

Who's influencing the conversation?

INFLUENCER OVERVIEW

Most active author

Yantocool
Online News Other
29.8K Posts

Most influential author

Donut Media
YouTube
1.3M Engagement

Most active site

domzale.info
Online News Other
29.8K Posts

Most influential site

www.breitbart.com
Online News Other
362.3K Engagement

MOST ACTIVE AUTHORS

MOST INFLUENTIAL SITES

| Influencer | Network | Posts |
|--|---|---|---|---|--|
| | 106 |
| 20.1K% |
| 18.6K% |
| | 55 |
| | 122 |
| 11.3K% |
	10
	135
	100

Where is the conversation coming from?

DISTRIBUTION ON THE WORLD MAP

SHARE OF COUNTRIES/REGIONS

- 4401% ● United States
- 1689% ● United Kingdom 2656% ● India
- 1911% ● Canada 5808% ● South Africa
- 14837% ● Australia 4513% ● Netherlands
- 4553% ● Indonesia 998% ● Germany
- 4436% ● Other

REACH VS ENGAGEMENT BY COUNTRY

What are people saying?

TRENDING POSTS

Author	Post	Trending Score	Other Metrics
	3/10	Sentiment Positive Twitter Followers 196.2K Retweets 363 Twitter Shares N/A Twitter Likes 3.4K	
	2/10	Sentiment Neutral Twitter Followers 8.9K Retweets 13 Twitter Shares N/A Twitter Likes 33	
	2/10	Sentiment Negative Twitter Followers 40 Retweets 209 Twitter Shares N/A Twitter Likes 947	
	2/10	Sentiment Neutral	
	2/10	Sentiment Positive	

TOP SOCIAL RESULTS

- | | | |
|---|---|--------|
| | <p>\$8000 Junkyard V8 vs \$30,000 Crate V8 Engine Swap</p> <p>...support Donut. We appreciate it! Milwaukee Electric Tools 2550-20 M12 Rivet Tool (Bare Tool) ... enthusiasts. We are drivers, drifters, and car enthusiasts who love to tell...</p> | 213.8K |
| <p>Donut Media shared a video YouTube 08/07/22 14:00</p> | | |
| | <p>Is TATA better than Tesla? How TATA is making world class ...</p> <p>Electric vehicles today are not something unimaginable. We are increasingly seeing more ... thrusters. India's future is definitely electric. But we can certainly say that the EV fight will be interesting because...</p> | 148.5K |
| <p>Abhi and Niyu shared a video YouTube 08/05/22 16:45</p> | | |
| | <p>Porsche 918 Spyder v Red Bull MotoGP Bike: DRAG RACE</p> <p>...car or how to buy a car you've come to the right place! We're here to help you sell a car, buy a used car or buy a new car! ... is my car worth?' - we can help with that too, as we know how to value a car and we'll al...</p> | 138.1K |
| <p>carwow shared a video YouTube 09/07/22 10:04</p> | | |
| | <p>Oh look Electric Car Fuel! pic.twitter.com/p0JwHA7BW8</p> <p>Oh look Electric Car Fuel! pic.twitter.com/p0JwHA7BW8</p> | 106.3K |
| <p>@RobertELBowman shared an image Twitter published on 10/07/22 at 00:34</p> | | |

TOP NEWS RESULTS

- | | | |
|---|--|--------|
| | <p>Platinum Party: Prince George sings along to Sweet Caroline</p> <p>Queen + Adam Lambert have delivered an electric opening to the BBC's Platinum Party at the Palace concert with a selection... Derby Day was missing the Queen, who has suffered a recurrence of her mobility proble...</p> | 181.9K |
| <p>stephanie linning for mailonline created a post Newspaper 04/06/22 22:31</p> | | |
| | <p>Electric Cars, Solar & Clean Energy Tesla Australia</p> <p>Solar and Powerwall Rebates are now available in selected states on Powerwall and solar. Learn more Rebates are now available in selected states on Powerwall and solar. Learn more</p> | 117.6K |
| <p>created a post Online News Other 05/06/22 02:36</p> | | |
| | <p>...drives into electric car problem: a replacement battery costs...</p> <p>...a used electric vehicle: the replacement battery for their dead car wound up costing more than the used car was purchased ... out that the car's battery would need to be replaced. The problem? A battery for the ele...</p> | 105.3K |
| <p>adam sables created a post TV/Radio 18/07/22 03:50</p> | | |
| | <p>WSJ Electric Vehicle Road Trip a Disaster</p> <p>...in an electric vehicle (EV) that ended up as a disaster — one that left the author grateful for her ordinary car, even at ... electric vehicle proved almost impossible, saving just \$100 and costing hours. At several points...</p> | 94.4K |
| <p>joel b. pollak created a post Online News Other 07/06/22 14:12</p> | | |

TOP SOCIAL RESULTS

- | | | |
|--|---|-------|
| | \$1500 vs \$8000 Drift Suspension | 97K |
| ...support Donut. We appreciate it! Milwaukee Electric Tools 2550-20 M12 Rivet Tool (Bare Tool) ... enthusiasts. We are drivers, drifters, and car enthusiasts who love to tell... | | |
| Donut Media shared a video YouTube 15/07/22 14:00 | | |
| | We Bought More Dumb Car Stuff from Wish.com | 96K |
| ...support Donut. We appreciate it! Milwaukee Electric Tools 2550-20 M12 Rivet Tool (Bare Tool) ... enthusiasts. We are drivers, drifters, and car enthusiasts who love to tell... | | |
| Donut Media shared a video YouTube 06/05/22 14:00 | | |
| | We Installed a Wish.com Supercharger on Our Car | 91.6K |
| ...demon clone? Or will it become just another car sitting in our parking lot that doesnt run? See if our Volkswagen makes more ... a4 Previous videos: We Bought More Dumb Car Stuff from Wish.com: https://www.y... | | |
| Donut Media shared a video YouTube 04/07/22 14:00 | | |
| | Why Did our 350Z Blow Up? An Investigation | 80.1K |
| ...support Donut. We appreciate it! Milwaukee Electric Tools 2550-20 M12 Rivet Tool (Bare Tool) ... enthusiasts. We are drivers, drifters, and car enthusiasts who love to tell... | | |
| Donut Media shared a video YouTube 15/06/22 14:00 | | |

TOP NEWS RESULTS

- | | | |
|---|---|-------|
| | Journalist attempts road trip in electric car, ends up spendin... | 88.4K |
| ...brand-new Kia EV6 to test America's current electric vehicle capabilities and public-charging infrastructure. By the end of ... have paid in a similarly-sized gas-fueled vehicle. However, "That \$100 savings cost us many..." | | |
| phil shiver created a post Online News Other 07/06/22 17:36 | | |
| | Report: Replacing Battery for EV Costs More than Car Itself, ... | 61.5K |
| ...type of electric vehicle. He issued a warning to anyone who was thinking about buying an electric vehicle. "If you're ... supporting the cars," he told WTSP. Despite the reliability and financial problems electric vehicles..." | | |
| ethan letkeman created a post Online News Other 18/07/22 14:58 | | |
| | ...Converts an Old Abandoned Tortoise Car to an Expensive R... | 42.7K |
| ...abandoned vintage cars into wonders The young man again acquired an old abandoned tortoise car, revamped it and has now sold ... vintage car? Can you scale this to refurbish few hundreds in a week? Can you take..." | | |
| victor duru created a post Online News Other 15/06/22 13:32 | | |
| | California Bullet Train Gets \$4.2 Billion Green Light For First... | 41.1K |
| ...viaducts and other structures on which electric trains will someday run at over 200 mph are being built—bringing temporary ... help cut climate-warming emissions from cars. The California project, which estimates ... | | |
| forbes staff created a post Magazine 16/07/22 12:30 | | |

TOP SOCIAL RESULTS

[First Look at the 2023 Civic Type R](#)

79.4K

...support Donut. We appreciate it! Milwaukee Electric Tools 2550-20 M12 Rivet Tool (Bare Tool) ... enthusiasts. We are drivers, drifters, and car enthusiasts who love to tell...

[Donut Media](#) | shared a video | YouTube | [21/07/22 04:00](#)

[We Stole a Tesla with this \\$20 Device](#)

75.7K

...support Donut. We appreciate it! Milwaukee Electric Tools 2550-20 M12 Rivet Tool (Bare Tool) ... enthusiasts. We are drivers, drifters, and car enthusiasts who love to tell...

[Donut Media](#) | shared a video | YouTube | [13/07/22 14:00](#)

TOP NEWS RESULTS

[...lesson when electric vehicle battery suddenly dies, replac...](#)

40.5K

...electric vehicles over gas-powered cars. "We're for cutting the cost of electric vehicles because when you have an electric ... to be able to get an EV." Indeed, electric vehicles are out-of-reach for most Americans unl...

[chris enloe](#) | created a post | Online News Other | [18/07/22 22:20](#)

[Times Top10: Today's Top News Headlines and Latest News f...](#)

38.4K

More here What: As the Niti Aayog steps up to finalise the 'Battery Swapping Policy' for electric vehicles (EVs), automobile industry and some government departments have flagged their concerns over the plan to fix ...

[various](#) | created a post | Newspaper | [10/06/22 15:57](#)

TOP BLOG RESULTS

- [A Postcard From a Mediterranean Cruise – Part 1](#) 4.2K
 ...your luggage from your car to the ship while a man checks your car for bumps and scratches, so that they don't get the blame. They give you a receipt for the car, a driver then takes it off to the car park and you go...
- Going Postal | created a post | Blogs | [17/07/22 09:00](#)
- [Nostalgia Album, Part Seventeen](#) 3.8K
 ...previously. My own attempt dates me. Not an electric car in sight. Towards the bottom and slightly to the left, a... We shall assume this is the exact spot where the car was parked, although concrete bollards now pr...
- Always Worth Saying | created a post | Blogs | [04/06/22 20:00](#)
- [Larry's Diary, Week One Hundred and Forty Two](#) 3.8K
 ...converting 50 armoured vehicles into field ambulances. The armoured vehicles are a gift from the U.K. and Venari are ... ventilation and insulation and domestic electric vehicle charging points. I hear that Emirates Ai...
- Going Postal | created a post | Blogs | [08/05/22 09:00](#)
- [The War Correspondent, Part One](#) 3.7K
 ...vainly trying to unload their tanks and vehicles on the Rhino Ferries [see Note 1 below]. Each time the ferries came up to... Our ferry arrived and shot upward past the open bows like a huge electric lift. As it subsided...
- Going Postal | created a post | Blogs | [05/05/22 19:00](#)

TOP FORUM RESULTS

- [American Polttics Xiii: \(un\)lucky For Some](#) 5.1K
 ...etc. for anyone wanting a zero-emissions vehicle, provide incentives for zero-emission transit and school buses, promote zero-emission vanpools, and improve access to electric bikes. CARB would be required to dist...
- Shrillland | created a post | Forums | [11/07/22 20:13](#)
- [Electric Vehicles are measurably reducing global oil demand; by...](#) 4.3K
<https://leva-eu.com/electric-vehicles-are-measurably-reducing-global-oil-demand-by-1-5-million-barrels-a-day/#:~:text=Approximately%201.5%20million%20barrels>
- Sweep145 | shared a link | Forums | [04/06/22 20:10](#)
- [GM cuts cost of electric vehicles by \\$6,000](#) 3.2K
http://www.reddit.com/r/technology/comments/v9vmeo/gm_cuts_cost_of_electric_vehicles_by_6000/
- Wagamaga | shared a link | Forums | [11/06/22 13:29](#)
- [Americans want more electric vehicles, but 50% by 2030 look...](#) 2.8K
<https://arstechnica.com/cars/2022/06/interest-in-evs-is-booming-but-us-still-lags-behind-europe-and-china/>
- Sorin61 | shared a link | Forums | [05/06/22 14:59](#)

TOP BLOG RESULTS

- [Larry's Diary, Week One Hundred And Forty One](#) 3.4K
...shows the car in question parked not in the disabled bay but in the next bay. It's not as if a bit of the car was ... repair will be carried out under warranty. A car dealer could make a lot of money never ever having any...
 Going Postal | created a post | Blogs | [01/05/22 09:00](#)
- [The 7/6 Day Thread Remembers Joy – The Avocado](#) 3.2K
1 We got our refund check back from the state in which I live, and it's a nice one. Sales of electric cars are rising rapidly. So is the use of energy which is not derived from fossil fuels. This is according to Spectrum mag...
 Lynn McKenzie | created a post | Blogs | [06/07/22 13:15](#)
- [Nostalgia Album, Part Eighteen](#) 2.8K
A 400-mile drive to Dover, culminating in your car being placed on the deck of a boat by a crane, doesn't appeal either. As ... the help of a twenty-minute frequency electric service. Although unlikely to get a laugh, To...
 Always Worth Saying | created a post | Blogs | [11/06/22 20:00](#)
- [...Their Gas-Powered Vehicles in Favor of \\$65,000 Electric Veh...](#) 2K
...forcing people to switch to electric vehicles during an appearance on REAL 92.3's show Big Boy TV. "We're for cutting the cost of electric vehicles because when you have an electric vehicle, then you're also going t...
 cristina laila | created a post | Blogs | [20/07/22 12:49](#)

TOP FORUM RESULTS

- [North Carolina Republicans Push Bill Forcing Towns To Destro...](#) 2.1K
http://www.reddit.com/r/technology/comments/vyyy2q/north_carolina_republicans_pus_h_bill_forcing/
 Sorin61 | shared a link | Forums | [14/07/22 17:43](#)
- [...don't you just buy a \\$45,000.00 electric car?" asks very help...](#) 1.6K
http://www.reddit.com/r/canada/comments/vek351/if_gas_prices_are_hurting_your_wallet_so_bad_why/
 cdnflower | shared a link | Forums | [17/06/22 18:34](#)
- [Biden to require electric vehicle charging stations every 50 m...](#) 1.1K
President Joe Biden has pledged to have 500,000 public charging stations for electric vehicles in place by 2030. The administration is providing more than \$5 billion to states over the next five years to build a network of...
 battle_rael | created a post | Forums | [09/06/22 18:29](#)
- [Ford CEO Jim Farley states electric vehicles will be sold 100% ...](#) 1.1K
<https://apple.news/AKsdutb04SMqI5fSP29LpRQ>
 edinburghiloveyou44 | shared a link | Forums | [02/06/22 02:26](#)

TOP BLOG RESULTS

 [Electric Cars Are Now Being Targeted For Overloading The Ele...](#) 1.9K
...asked owners in Texas not to charge their cars during a heat wave to help avoid blackouts and overloading the state's failing power grid. The alert comes as the Electric Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT) called on...

michael robison | created a post | Blogs | [14/07/22 10:45](#)

 [Larry's Diary, Week One Hundred And Fifty](#) 1.8K
...their next car, petrol, diesel or electric. 77% said anything but electric. Has the public seen through the greenwash at last? Electric cars are not cheap, on average they were 50% more expensive to buy than the eq...

Going Postal | created a post | Blogs | [03/07/22 14:21](#)

TOP FORUM RESULTS

 [...logistics kept them from buying an electric car](#) 1.1K
http://www.reddit.com/r/technology/comments/vvqwk2/survey_suggests_majority_of_americans_say/

Sorin61 | shared a link | Forums | [10/07/22 14:55](#)

 [is anyone just tired of living anymore? \(Not suicidal\)](#) 932
...winning or even getting close. Gas is unobtainable at this point. Can't afford an electric car. So fuck me. Can't take the family on vacation (first world problem I know but it's a pride thing and a memory thing for me)...

spcmiddleton | created a post | Forums | [08/06/22 02:49](#)